

SETTING OF BOUNDARY CONDITIONS FOR A THREE-LAYER PLATE

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We consider the boundary conditions when the edges of the plate are fixed in different ways.

1) *Clamping condition.* Let the $x=0$ sides on axis y be firmly fixed. In this

Figure 1. Three-layer plate with double-sided fastening

direction, there are no displacements and no rotations relative to axis y

$$x=0 \text{ at } w=0, \frac{\partial w}{\partial y} = 0. \quad (1)$$

Figure 2. Three-layer plate with hinges on both sides

2) *Hinged condition.* For the

hinged side,

$$w=0, \text{ va } M_x = 0, \quad (2)$$

or, this is through migrations,

$$w=0, \frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial x^2} + \mu \frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial y^2} = 0$$

from on this side $y = \text{const}$ from

being $\frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial y^2} = 0$ it is known, it follows

that the boundary condition is as follows.

$$w=0, \quad \frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial x^2} = 0$$

3) *Boundary conditions for a free-standing edge.*

In this case, the bending moment M_y , the transverse free force Q_y the torsional moment M_{xy} become zero. It's not 2 conditions but 3 conditions. When solving the problem, 2 boundary conditions must be given. To eliminate this conflict, we combine the last two terms into one.

Figure 3. A free-standing three-layer plate

We show that at the limit, the torque and the transverse free force are represented by a single force. These forces are statically equivalent torque M_{xy} x parallel to the axis dx torque in length $M_{xy}dx$ is equal to. M_{xy} If we look at dx vertically in the direction of $(M_{xy} + \frac{\partial M_{xy}}{\partial x} dx)dx$ is equal to.

Each dx into an infinitesimal fraction $\frac{\partial M_{xy}}{\partial x} dx$ fits. So the power in each distribution is equal to $\frac{\partial M_{xy}}{\partial x}$. The forces generated at points C and B, the vertical load are reduced to the transverse free force. Transverse free force acting on CB;

$$Q_y^k = Q_y + \frac{\partial M_{xy}}{\partial x} \text{ and } Q_x^k = Q_x + \frac{\partial M_{xy}}{\partial y} \quad (3)$$

If we express the third equation of the equilibrium equation by differentiating x and y displacements;

$$\frac{\partial M_{xy}}{\partial x} = D(1-\mu) \frac{\partial^3 w}{\partial x^2 \partial y}; \text{ and } \frac{\partial M_{xy}}{\partial y} = D(1-\mu) \frac{\partial^3 w}{\partial y^2 \partial x}, \quad (4)$$

Taking (4) into account, we get the following $x = 0$ side is free, then the boundary condition for this side is obtained as follows.

$$Q_y^k = D \left[\frac{\partial^3 w}{\partial x^3} + (2-\mu) \frac{\partial^3 w}{\partial y^2 \partial x} \right]; \quad Q_x^k = D \left[\frac{\partial^3 w}{\partial y^3} + (2-\mu) \frac{\partial^3 w}{\partial x^2 \partial y} \right].$$

Similarly, at the edges of the plate, the three conditions, bending moment, torsional moment, and transverse free force are treated as only two bending moments and the given transverse free force.

$$M_y = 0 \text{ and } Q_y^k = 0$$

this relation is written by transpositions as follows:

$$\frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial x^2} + \mu \frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial y^2} = 0, \quad \frac{\partial^3 w}{\partial x^3} + (2-\mu) \frac{\partial^3 w}{\partial x \partial y^2} = 0.$$

It can be seen from here that the boundary conditions with the edges of the plate resting freely are more complicated than the previous ones.

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